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Agri-food competitiveness in the Andean Community: a study of revealed comparative advantage indices

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ABSTRACT

Despite growth and trade agreements in the Andean Community, the competitiveness of agri-food exports from member countries has not been fully assessed. This study quantifies the competitiveness of these exports during the period 2013–2023 by applying the Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) index and a subsequent statistical correlation test to validate the robustness of the data. The results highlight Ecuador as the only country with a significant degree of competitiveness in its agri-food exports. Throughout the period analysed, the countries of the Andean Community show differences in the competitiveness of their agri-food exports, which are mainly reflected in their RCA indices. Ecuador stands out for its high RCA, indicating strong competitiveness, while other countries such as Colombia, Bolivia, and Peru have indices below 1, indicating challenges in innovation and diversification that affect their position in the global agri-food market.

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Introduction

Competitiveness, as defined by the World Economic Forum (WEF), encompasses a set of elements that include institutions, policies, and factors that determine the level of productivity of an economy, which in turn determines the level of prosperity that a country can achieve (Matkovski et al., 2021). However, trade theory, argues that a nation's competitiveness is based on the principle of comparative advantage (Latruffe, 2010).

The competitiveness of agri-food products is a crucial factor in boosting exports and promoting economic growth, especially in emerging economies (Dimitrijevic et al., 2023). In the same vein Bula (2020) mentions that it contributes to poverty eradication, increased productivity, job creation, and better wages for workers in the sector. When analysing the competitiveness of agri-food systems, it is important to consider that it is developed at several levels that support each other, given that the competitive products produced by companies influence their capacity for growth, investment, and innovation, which define the competitiveness of the company (Ayazbayeva Gulnara et al., 2024).

In the 21st century, international trade has grown rapidly, benefiting the food sector. In 2015, the OECD and FAO predicted that the demand for food in developing countries would increase due to population growth, rising per capita income, and urbanisation (Esteve-Llorens et al., 2022). In this scenario, Latin America (LATAM), including the Caribbean, is considered a food exporting region, responsible for 14% of the world's production of agricultural and fishery products (Granillo-Macías et al., 2024).

The relevance of competitiveness research lies in its ability to help countries formulate policies to promote and improve their competitive positions (Escalante Yaulilahua et al., 2023; Gavrilescu & Voicilaş,

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2014). Latin America is expected to double its share of agri-food production by 2028, with a growth of 28%, making it the world's leading region in food exports (Granillo-Macías et al., 2024). The originality of this research lies in a relatively novel approach to identify the degree of competitiveness and position of the Andean Community (CAN) countries in respect to their agri-food exports according to the agri-food section to identify the comparative advantages of the agri-food sector exports of CAN members, considering their export performance.

This study assesses the competitiveness of agri-food exports from member countries of the Andean Community during the period 2013-2023. Accordingly, the following general hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis: At least one member country maintains a significant level of competitiveness in its agri-food exports.

This general premise gives rise to *four specific hypotheses*:

- *H1*. Colombia demonstrates a significant level of competitiveness in its agri-food exports during the period 2013-2023.
- *H2*. Ecuador shows a significant level of competitiveness in its agri-food exports during the period 2018-2023.
- *H3*. Bolivia exhibits a significant level of competitiveness in its agri-food exports during the period 2013-2023.
- *H4*. Peru maintains a significant level of competitiveness in its agri-food exports during the period 2013-2023.

This analysis aims to provide a comparative and empirical perspective on the competitive dynamics of the member countries of the Andean Community, thus contributing to a deeper understanding of the factors driving their agri-food exports.

Theoretical framework

Literature on the competitiveness of agri-food exports from the member countries of the Andean Community (CAN) encompasses a wide range of concepts, approaches, and theories that form the basis of this theoretical framework. This analysis begins with the definition of competitiveness, followed by a detailed examination of agri-food exports. Next, it addresses the influence of competitiveness on exports by specifying the products included in this category. Finally, the information gathered is correlated to assess how these factors impact the competitiveness of agri-food exports.

Competitiveness

First, Porter (1990) defines competitiveness as the ability to innovate and create competitive advantages through important attributes such as labour costs, interest rates, exchange rates, and economies of scale which in turn has a greater number of technical regulations improving market competitiveness (Mwatu et al., 2024). According to Momaya and Selby (1998), the competitiveness of a country, sector, or firm lies in its ability to create an enabling environment that promotes business growth and profitable investment as well as its ability to compete internationally by offering superior products in terms of quality and price.

On the contrary, Lombana and Gutiérrez (2009) mention that at a microeconomic level, competitiveness is quantitatively evaluated through productivity indicators, profit margins, and profits, while qualitatively, it is evaluated through management strategies. Furthermore, Santacruz et al. (2019) indicate that it depends on technological capabilities, innovation in production, efficiency in the use of available resources, and other factors implemented by actors involved in the primary production sector. Similarly, competitiveness is described as the ability of a company to promote customer loyalty, considering in this case its positioning, communication, and positive image in the eyes of the consumer (Tang et al., 2024).

Agri-food exports

The analysis by Matkovski et al. (2021) is worth highlighting; it concerns the fundamental role of the agri-food sector in the economies of all countries, which is essential for economic and social stability. Thus, exports of agri-food products worldwide have experienced significant growth (Bojnec & Ferto, 2015).

In this context, increasing economic globalisation makes internationalisation vital for the success of agri-food companies. Despite being promoted as beneficial, entering international markets involves initial challenges and costs (Serrano et al., 2018). Agri-food supply chain is an important component of this sector; it is globalised and requires managerial knowledge of international trade, and the complex web of regulations and stakeholders that influence commodity production in most countries (Sporleder & Boland, 2011).

Solutions to these challenges are currently being proposed. For example, Charlebois et al. (2024) indicate that the implementation of digital traceability in the agri-food industry is undergoing a global transformation, with varying levels of progress and adoption in different countries generating relevant information on the future of the agri-food sector. The success of its resolution is attributed not only to the diversity and quality of the products but also to their remarkable degree of competitiveness; non-food products are also included, and a significant degree of transformation in this sector is observable (Silva et al., 2009).

Competitiveness of the agri-food sector

Globally, challenges exist in providing healthy and nutritious food, with the agri-food sector being a fundamental pillar in this regard. The FAO is partnering with developing countries to generate competitiveness and implement agricultural and food innovation systems (Reyes Arias, n.d.). Agri-food products with a designation of origin, indications of origin, and geographical indications are differentiators that favour the export offer, provide added value, and position in national and international markets, thus representing the competitive agri-food level of a country (Toledo-Macas & Zumba-Zuniga, 2021).

In addition, Bojnec & Ferto (2015) mention that agricultural production is key in the agri-food sector, due to soil quality, climatic conditions and natural resources, which are important to enter more competitive markets, and to achieve trade freedom, long-term survival must be achieved. However, the current agri-food system in developing countries is a major agent of deforestation and pollution of soil, air, and water; they impact greenhouse gas emissions, which have a major impact on the environment (Camacho, 2017).

Technology plays an important role in the operation of a country's agri-food sector as it is necessary to supply food to international markets and develop the agricultural market (Clemente, 2021). Furthermore, digitalisation of the agri-food industry is a relevant topic today. This sector uses different types of robots to optimise production and decrease the reliance on labour, an example of which is the development of smart sensors based on spectroscopic technology used to improve food quality (Wójcicki et al., 2024).

Revealed competitive advantage (RCA) index

RCA helps in assessing a country's trade performance in terms of its export structure and export/import ratios by identifying products with a competitive advantage, which is manifested in a higher proportion of exports of those products compared to other countries (Balassa, 1965).

Conversely, Arias-Segura and Segura-Ruiz (2004) refer to the competition between producers of a specific good for domestic resources in contrast to other goods produced and traded in the country as well as the country's ability to compete in the international market for that product. Similarly, the trade competitiveness of a sector is defined as the ability to achieve a profitable participation in international markets, analysing the theory of comparative advantage explained by the classical theory in the competitiveness of a country or region according to the availability of natural resources and manufacturing factors (Lugo Arias, 2017).

Methodology

Competitiveness analysis is based on annual export data for 24 products within the agricultural export sector of the CAN member countries for the period 2013-2023. Export data were obtained from Euromonitor, and product divisions within the agricultural sector were used to calculate the competitiveness of each of the countries that make up the regional bloc.

The selection of 24 tariff lines from the agro-export sector of the Andean Community, based on the Andean harmonised classification, was aimed at ensuring a representative sample that captures the diversity and economic significance of the sector in the region. This decision was supported by solid precedents, such as the study by Gavrilesco and Voicilaş (2014), who employed the same tariff lines in the analyses of other integration models, such as the European Union. The selection of these tariff lines provided a comprehensive understanding of the main exported products and their impact on the trade balance of the Andean Community member countries, facilitating a comparative analysis of export patterns and competitive advantages.

Most researchers prefer to use a standardised measure of net export shares, known as RCA and developed by Balassa (1965), to determine the comparative advantage of a certain commodity or product in the market. Siew-Ling Liew et al. (2021). This is because the RCA index is one of the most accurate ways of calculating the competitiveness of a country in terms of its exports (Matkovski et al., 2021). Balassa established the calculation of the RCA index as follows.

$$RCA_{ij} = \frac{\frac{X_{ij}}{X_{it}}}{\frac{X_{nj}}{X_{nt}}}$$

Here, X represents exports, i refers to the country, j indicates the sector or division, t represents total exports, and n denotes the group of countries being compared.

The RCA index compares competitiveness between countries and their respective regions (Lugo-Arias et al., 2024). Thus, the mathematical formula considers country and regional (or trade bloc) variables. According to Matkovski et al. (2021) when the value of the RCA index is greater than three, comparative advantages are strong; RCA index values between two and three indicate considerable significance, whereas RCA values between one and two imply satisfactory comparative advantages for comprehensive details, please refer to Table 1).

Wang et al. (2023) argue that this approach can be further developed using a value chain perspective to assess the export competitiveness of products. However, it requires a complete value chain that is not present in developing countries. Thus, the RCA index is criticised by researchers because of its limited accuracy when considering factors such as changes in economic policies in each country (Siew-Ling Liew et al., 2021). However, Vollrath (1991) developed a new specification of comparative advantages revealed in the form of relative trade advantages (RTA), which are calculated as the difference between relative export advantages (RXA) and relative import advantages (RMP) (Bayav & Şahin, 2023):

$$RTA = RXA - RMP \quad (1)$$

Table 1. Description of RCA variables by exports.

Variables	Description	Source
Dependent		
RCA	Refers to the Revelance Comparative Advantage index.	(Balassa, 1965)
Independent		
X_{ij}	It represents each country's agri-food exports, broken down into animal, plant, and non-food products.	Euromonitor
X_{it}	It represents the total exports of each country, covering all sectors.	Euromonitor
X_{nj}	It represents the exports of the agri-food sector of the member countries of the Andean Community, broken down by section.	Euromonitor
X_{nt}	It represents the total exports of the agri-food sector of the member countries of the Andean Community.	Euromonitor

where,

$$RXA=RCA \quad (2)$$

In addition,

$$RMP_{ij} = \frac{\frac{M_{ij}}{M_{it}}}{\frac{M_{nj}}{M_{nt}}} \quad (3)$$

Here, “M” represents imports, “i” refers to the country, “j” indicates the sector or division, “t” represents total exports, and “n” denotes the group of countries being compared. According to Bayav and Şahin (2023), unlike the index mentioned above, when the value of RMP exceeds one, the country is interpreted as having a relative disadvantage in the sector; a value less than or equal to one indicates a relative advantage (for comprehensive details, please refer to Table 2).

On the contrary, the RCA index proposed by Balassa has faced challenges due to its asymmetry (Lugo-Arias et al., 2024). This characteristic has led authors such as Vollrath (1991) to propose the revealed competitiveness (RC) index, which is composed of three revealed competitive advantages, followed by a competitiveness analysis and calculation using logarithms (lnRXA) (Duana-Avila et al., 2023). It is calculated as follows:

$$RC = \ln RXA - \ln RMP \quad (4)$$

When $RC > 0$, the sections or divisions have comparative advantages. A value below zero indicates a net competitive disadvantage of the country in question (Paluš et al., 2015). The index RC comprises both exports and imports, which are more compatible with real-world trade (Yusefzadeh et al., 2015).

Some authors suggest using specific statistical tests to determine the extent to which different indices of comparative advantage are consistent (Matkovski et al., 2021). For example, Guaita-Pradas et al. (2023) conducted an analysis of variance to determine whether the indices were statistically different; in addition, they studied the existence of correlations between the indices as well as the extent of these correlations, which provides information on the degree or level of relationship between the indices.

Results

The agri-food sector is a part of the economies of CAN member countries, and its marked impact on total exports has been demonstrated. In this case, a graph was developed with total exports and the participation of agri-food products for each CAN country to analyse the importance of the agri-food sector between 2013 and 2023. The agri-food sector is important in the exports of a country, mainly in the CAN member countries, and it has a greater participation in the total exports (Figure 1) of Ecuador (49.60%), followed by Peru (21.92%), Colombia (19.07%), and Bolivia (18.49%); the averages in the period analysed are shown. In absolute terms, the largest exporter of agri-food products among the CAN member countries in the period

Table 2. Description of RMP variables according to imports.

Variables	Description	Source
Dependent		
<i>RMP</i>	Refers to the relative import penetration index	(Vollrath, 1991)
Independent		
<i>M_{ij}</i>	It represents each country's agri-food imports, broken down into animal, plant, and non-food products.	Euromonitor
<i>M_{it}</i>	It represents the total imports of each country, covering all sectors.	Euromonitor
<i>M_{nj}</i>	It represents the imports of the agri-food sector of the member countries of the Andean Community, broken down by section.	Euromonitor
<i>M_{nt}</i>	It represents the total imports of the agri-food sector of the member countries of the Andean Community.	Euromonitor

Figure 1. Exports of agri-food products from the CAN countries. *Note.* Prepared by the authors using data obtained from the Euromonitor database (2013–2023). **Figure 1** shows the trend in the exports of agri-food products by the CAN member countries from 2013 to 2023.

analysed is Ecuador (127,243 million dollars), followed by Peru (118,404.95 million dollars), Colombia (88,752.15 million dollars), and Bolivia (20,619.46 million dollars). All CAN member countries saw an increase in respect of the dynamics of agri-food products during the period analysed.

Figure 1. Continued.

Table 3. Breakdown of exported products from the agri-food sector of CAN member countries.

Products covered by type of agro-exports	Peru	Ecuador	Colombia	Bolivia
Section 1 - Animal and animal products	10.75%	36.87%	5.60%	4.50%
00 - Live animals	0.07%	0.01%	1.83%	0.00%
01-Meat and edible meat offal	0.08%	0.00%	1.40%	2.80%
02- Crustaceans, molluscs, and aquatic invertebrates	9.61%	36.79%	1.72%	0.00%
03 - Eggs, honey and other animal Foodstuffs	0.93%	0.04%	0.24%	1.63%
04 - Other animal products	0.06%	0.03%	0.41%	0.07%
Section 2 - Plant products	56.23%	39.70%	76.39%	54.00%
06 - Live trees, plants, bulbs, roots, cut flowers	0.20%	7.55%	19.02%	0.02%
07 - Edible vegetables, some roots, and tubers	6.60%	1.55%	0.27%	1.24%
08 - Fruits, nuts, citrus peels	30.60%	27.76%	14.02%	11.07%
09 - Coffee, tea, mate, and spices	9.47%	0.28%	34.44%	0.63%
10 - Cereals	1.49%	0.18%	0.11%	5.63%
11 - Milling products, malt, starches, inulin, glutinous wheat	0.37%	0.06%	0.66%	0.22%
12 - Oily seeds, oilseeds, oleaginous fruits, grains, seeds	1.50%	0.06%	0.42%	10.25%
13 - Gums, resins, vegetable extracts and other extracts	0.37%	0.00%	0.03%	0.00%
14 - Strands and other plant products	0.38%	0.02%	0.01%	0.01%
15 - Animals, vegetable fats, and oils	5.23%	2.24%	7.41%	24.93%
Section 3 - Non-food products	33.02%	23.44%	18.01%	41.51%
17 - Other meat, fish and other seafood preparations	2.71%	10.56%	0.35%	0.36%
18 - Sugar and other sugar confectionery	0.77%	0.47%	7.31%	2.01%
19 - Cocoa and cocoa preparations	2.68%	6.91%	1.47%	0.12%
20 - Cereal, flour, starch, milk preparations and milk products	1.73%	0.15%	1.81%	0.84%
21 - Vegetables, fruit, and nuts	6.12%	2.18%	1.09%	0.92%
22 - Miscellaneous edible preparations	0.92%	1.00%	4.57%	0.03%
23 - Brews, liqueurs, and vinegars	1.42%	0.16%	0.44%	3.37%
24 - Waste, industrial food waste, animal feed	16.64%	1.40%	0.55%	33.84%
25 - Tobacco and tobacco substitutes	0.04%	0.62%	0.42%	0.00%

Note. Prepared by the authors with the data obtained from the Euromonitor database (2013–2023). Table 3 shows the breakdown of the agri-food products of the CAN member countries.

The data affirms high participation and development in the agri-food sector in Ecuador, but in the rest of the CAN countries, it has not represented a large part of their exports; thus, it can be assumed that the agri-food sector is not the basis of their respective economies. Therefore, there is limited growth in the period analysed in Colombia, Bolivia, and Peru because economic policies do not prioritise the export sector. However, they should focus on the growth of local production, technology, and direct and indirect subsidies to investors, attracting new investment, promotion, and information to encourage the export sector (Carvajal & López, 2021).

Different shares are observed in the three main sections—animal, vegetable, and non-food products—in the structure of agri-food exports from Peru, Ecuador, Colombia, and Bolivia (Table 3).

In the animal products section (Section 1), Ecuador leads with a significant share (36.87%) of its agri-food exports, with the division of crustaceans, mollusks, and aquatic invertebrates standing out in particular.

According to the report *Exportaciones Intra y Extra Comunitarias de Productos Agrícolas y Pesquero* (Andean Community, 2017), the high impact of Ecuador's exports of fishery products is evident; in 2016, it accounted for 64.1% of the Andean Community's exports of fishery products to the world. In contrast, Peru, Colombia, and Bolivia show lower shares in this section with 10.75%, 5.60%, and 4.50%, respectively.

The vegetable products section (Section 2) is dominant in most countries. Colombia has the highest share (76.39%), followed by Peru (56.23%), Bolivia (54.00%), and Ecuador (39.70%). The most exported products are fruits, nuts, and citrus peels, with Peru and Ecuador standing out in this category. On the contrary, Colombia excels in the export of coffee, tea, mate, and spices; its tropical climate and diversity of altitudes allow for a variety of crops, which has led to these products being traditionally recognised as Colombia's main export goods (SICEX, 2022). Finally, Bolivia's export of oilseeds and other grains is notable (10.25%).

In regards the non-food products section (Section 3), Bolivia has the highest share (41.51%), followed by Peru (33.02%), Ecuador (23.44%), and Colombia (18.01%). The division of miscellaneous edible products in Bolivia is particularly significant. The exports of other meat, fish, and other seafood preparations are relevant (10.56%) in Ecuador. In Peru, the export of sugars and other sugar confectioneries stands out at 2.68%, whereas in Colombia, the export of industrial food waste and residues, and animal feed represents 7.33%.

The values of the index of comparative advantages of agri-food products in the member countries of the CAN economic bloc (Figure 2) suggest that at least one of the CAN member countries has a comparative advantage in agri-exports during the study period. The analysis of the comparative advantages of the agri-food products of the countries constituting the CAN bloc suggest that Ecuador has a higher index of comparative advantages in this sector than Bolivia, Peru, and Colombia, which show a constant stagnation in their comparative advantages during the study period.

The index of comparative advantages in Ecuador, with its highest RCA index in 2017 (5.02) and lowest in 2014 (3.11) in the period analysed, is highly competitive with respect to the other indices of the countries that make up CAN.

As for Bolivia, the graph (Figure 2) shows a constant stagnation with respect to its comparative advantages in the agri-food sector, with indices of less than 1 in the period analysed, with the highest index (0.95) in 2013. According to Santamaria Mendoza et al. (2022), Bolivia has inefficiencies in its political, economic, and social environments, lacking government support for agricultural production and marketing despite the importance of products such as soybeans. However, aquaculture does not play a significant role in Bolivia's economy (FAO, 2024).

The graph (Figure 2) shows that in Peru, the agri-food sector under the RCA index (which is less than 1) indicates that it has no satisfactory comparative advantages, with the exception of 2014, when its index was 1.0380. Escalante et al. (2022) note that blueberries have experienced steady growth; grapes

Figure 2. Revealed comparative advantages of the agri-food sector of the CAN countries. Source: Own research based on Euromonitor.

Note. Own elaboration with the data obtained from Euromonitor database (2013–2023).

and avocados have become more competitive; but coffee and asparagus show declines. These variations may be linked to production time, which affects market responsiveness.

According to RCA index, Colombia has low competitiveness; between 2013 and 2023, its performance changed little, with few positive changes. According to, Cubillos et al. (2021) traditional exports remain dominant, accounting for more than half of the total exports. However, dependence is centred on natural resources and mining, and the agri-food sector has lost its relevance.

The modified RCA indices reflect how the indicators of the comparative advantage of agri-food exports vary across the Andean Community countries. Some modified indicators may maintain different trends because the import values of the analysed products are included, whereas other indices use only export values.

For Ecuador, the RCA Index indicates a significant level of competitiveness and is strongly correlated with the logarithmic version of the index (lnRCA). The relative trade advantage (RTA) index also reflects a significant level of competitiveness and maintains a strong correlation with the rest of the modified indices except for the Revealed Competitiveness (RC) Index. The latter reflects an existing level of competitiveness in contrast to the significant level noted above and maintains a positively strong, albeit slightly lower, level of correlation.

The analysis of the modified indices for Colombia, Bolivia, and Peru does not show values indicating the existence of competitiveness in agri-food exports. In Bolivia, the RCA Index shows levels below the threshold, whereas some of its modifications suggest the possible existence of inconsistent competitiveness. Although the variability in some indices is high, the correlations between them are strong. In contrast, Colombia and Peru show indicators that do not reflect competitiveness with respect to their agri-food exports. The variability in the data for both countries does not indicate the existence of abruptly dispersed data, and a strong correlation is maintained (for comprehensive details, please refer to Table 4).

The data obtained from the RCA Index and modified indicators for the different Andean Community countries show strong levels of correlation that demonstrate the consistency of the assessment methods and underline the validity of the findings.

Discussion

The export performance of the agri-food sector of the Andean Community member countries is related to agricultural production and technology, which are important factors for the competitiveness of agri-food systems. This finding contrasts with Wójcicki et al. (2024), which suggests that technology and digitalisation are competitive factors for the agri-food industry and that the optimisation of production with different types of technology reduces the fixed labour costs in agri-food production systems. Clemente (2021) reinforces the concept of the use of technology as a tool in agri-food production, where manipulating production to achieve efficiency and increase sales margin is possible, given the use of new technologies. In contrast, Suroso et al. (2023) consider that the fundamental tool for the development of agri-food competitiveness is based on three digital indicators related to the Internet (infrastructure, security, and users), which are mainly responsible for promoting and maximising the commercialisation of agri-food in developing countries of the Andean Community. These approaches determine the competitiveness of the agri-food sector of a developing country in relation to developed countries, prioritising the use of technologies in agricultural production and technological tools as complements to production and internationalisation strategies to boost agri-food exports.

Hypothesis H1, which posited a significant level of competitiveness for Colombia during the period 2013–2023, faced evidence that suggested otherwise. The RCA index indicates that Colombia's level of competitiveness in the agri-food sector is low 0.56 (Figure 2), although the country had a strong focus on vegetable products, leading exports in this category by 79.39% during the study period (Table 3). This finding is consistent with Solarte-Montufar et al. (2021), which also identifies low competitiveness in the Colombian agri-food sector, attributing it to the fact that few companies have the resources or effective strategies to manage and apply innovation systematically. On the contrary, Arias and Alarcón (2019) showed more encouraging results, highlighting the importance of business collaboration and relational capital in increasing sales and managing value innovations. These diverse approaches underline the complexity of Colombia's agri-food sector, focusing on the need to strengthen innovation capabilities and

Table 4. Correlation analysis of the revealed comparative advantage index (RCA) and its changes in Andean Community agro-exports between 2013–2023.

Colombia				
Average 2013–2023	0.56	−0.62	−0.58	−0.74
Coefficient of variation	13.42%	−15.83%	−23.32%	−10.40%
<i>Correlation analysis</i>				
	RCA	RTA	lnRCA	RC
RCA	1			
RTA	0.4765	1		
lnRCA	0.9968	0.4616	1	
RC	0.8364	0.8746	0.8318	1
Ecuador				
Average 2013–2023	3.95	3.10	1.36	1.53
Coefficient of variation	15.91%	21.61%	11.71%	16.29%
<i>Correlation analysis</i>				
	RCA	RTA	lnRCA	RC
RCA	1			
RTA	0.9817	1		
lnRCA	0.9978	0.9795	1	
RC	0.7629	0.8708	0.7652	1
Bolivia				
Average 2013–2023	0.65	0.03	−0.46	0.03
Coefficient of variation	23.96%	852.03%	−49.69%	1042.38%
<i>Correlation analysis</i>				
	RCA	RTA	lnRCA	RC
RCA	1			
RTA	0.8578	1		
lnRCA	0.9949	0.8655	1	
RC	0.8278	0.9957	0.8432	1
Peru				
Average 2013–2023	0.7263	−0.3311	−0.4612	−0.3866
Coefficient of variation	19.17%	−29.33%	−38.78%	−33.91%
<i>Correlation analysis</i>				
	RCA	RTA	lnRCA	RC
RCA	1			
RTA	0.6708	1		
lnRCA	0.9957	0.6740	1	
RC	0.8418	0.9547	0.8535	1

Note. RCA > 1; RTA > 0; lnRCA > 0; RC > 0. Own research based on Euromonitor database.

business cooperation to improve competitiveness. However, it is important to note that no study has covered the challenges faced in rural areas in Colombia, where the adoption of technologies and innovation are limited by structural and socio-economic factors that affect the competitiveness of the sector (Arias & Alarcón, 2019). Therefore, future research should focus on developing methodologies that provide strategies to improve innovation and competitiveness in Colombia.

For Hypothesis H2, which stated that Ecuador exhibited a significant level of competitiveness between 2018 and 2023, the data provide supporting evidence. Ecuador is the only Andean Community country that shows a significant level of competitiveness in its agri-food exports, with an average AACR index of 3.95 over the study period (Figure 2). These results indicate a significant level of export competitiveness for this type of product. However, Ecuador presents a contrast to the concept of competitiveness expressed by Momaya and Selby (1998), who argue that the competitiveness of a country, sector, or firm depends on its ability to create conditions conducive to business development and profitable investment. Based on this assertion, Ecuador has demonstrated great effectiveness in creating a thriving environment for its agri-food exports between 2013 and 2023, resulting in a significant level of competitiveness. However, Emam et al. (2022) reported that Ecuador failed to create a prosperous environment for its agri-food exports between 2013 and 2023, which resulted in significant competitiveness. They also reported that Ecuador failed to implement the National Green Export Review (NGER) in 2015, which was supposed to be a key tool in the formulation of policies to improve export competitiveness and proved to be ineffective. Given this contrast, it is possible that the result obtained from the RCA index does not reflect the real competitiveness of the country but only an advantage over the rest of the comparator

countries. In the case of future research, in order to confirm the existence of a significant level of competitiveness for Ecuador's agri-food exports, it should be complemented with methodologies that allow an individual analysis of the country.

Hypothesis H3, which asserts that Bolivia demonstrated a significant level of competitiveness from 2013 to 2023, is refuted by the obtained results. In comparison, Bolivia presents an average RCA index of 0.65 over the period 2013–2023 (Figure 2), indicating low competitiveness in the agri-food sector, despite the growth registered in this sector (Table 3). This finding is consistent with the economic and trade report for Bolivia, prepared by ICEX (2024), which indicates that although exports in the primary sector have shown positive figures, the total results are still below the country's true competitive potential. This situation is attributed to environmental inefficiencies and a lack of government support (Santamaria Mendoza et al., 2022). Hence, for innovative processes in agri-food systems to develop and function efficiently, a set of public policies that implement technological innovation to modernise productive processes is necessary (Piñeiro & Trigo, 2024).

Finally, Hypothesis H4, which posited that Peru maintained a significant level of competitiveness from 2013 to 2023, presented a mixed outlook. Peru has the second highest share of exported products in the agri-food sector among the Andean Community member countries (21.92%) (Figure 1). Peru's average RCA index has been consistently lower than 1 (Figure 2), indicating that it did not have satisfactory comparative advantages throughout the years studied, except for 2014, when it exceeded its RCA index at 1.0380. This finding contradicts the findings of Escalante et al. (2023), who argue that Peru stands out for its remarkable competitiveness in the agri-food sector, which is attributed to favourable climatic conditions, abundant natural resources, and environmental spaces; these constitute significant natural advantages allowing the sector to preserve traditional methods that, with technological advances and research, have managed to expand national production and facilitate participation in international markets.

On the contrary, Yllescas-Rodriguez et al. (2021) report that Peru has made considerable efforts to increase its exports and enter the global market with products that meet the quality standards demanded by destination markets. However, the lack of diversification is a notable limitation as statistics indicate that approximately 60% of exports come from a single sector. Similarly, although this study shows that Peru is not highly competitive within the economic bloc, it has the potential and opportunities to become so; Boys et al. (2022) indicate that the trend analysis of trade in organic products between the United States and its partners reveals opportunities for Peru. Estela García et al. (2023) indicate that export diversification into emerging markets should be considered a vital economic strategy to reduce risks and foster long-term economic recovery.

Conclusions

First, Colombia's agri-food exports during the study period have shown considerable focus on vegetable products because of favourable climatic conditions. However, the country has a low RCA index, reflecting limited competitiveness in the agri-food sector, owing to a lack of resources and strategies for innovation and technology adoption.

Second, Ecuador exhibits a significant level of competitiveness in its agri-food exports, reflected in a high RCA index and its correlation with indices other than the RC index. However, the contrast between these results and the ineffectiveness of the National Green Export Review (NGER) suggests that this advantage may not represent real structural competitiveness.

Third, Bolivia has a low competitiveness in its CAN agri-food exports as reflected in its RCA index, which has consistently been below 1 despite its export growth in recent years. Political, economic, and social inefficiencies as well as a lack of government support have negatively affected the sector's competitiveness.

Fourth, the assessment of Peru's competitiveness in the Andean Community's agri-food sector is mostly negative, as its average RCA index has been consistently below 1, indicating low competitiveness, except in 2014. In addition, significant efforts to increase the exports of high-value products are noteworthy, although high dependence on a single export sector, which is a vulnerability, remains.

Fifth, the comparative nature of the RCA index was crucial in confirming the hypothesis that at least one Andean Community country maintains a significant degree of competitiveness in its agri-food

exports. Given that few studies address this issue specifically for the Andean Community countries, the analysis provides data and substantiated conclusions that help fill this knowledge gap on the competitiveness of the region's agri-food sector.

Finally, the use of the RCA Index has been instrumental in assessing these dynamics and provides a solid basis for future research seeking to deepen effective strategies for agri-food sector development in these countries. Additionally, continued analysis of the AACR Index over time will provide a dynamic perspective on the evolution of competitiveness, facilitating more precise strategic adjustments to strengthen the position of these countries in the global agri-food market.

Recommendations

First, to improve the competitiveness of Colombia's agri-food sector, it must strengthen its capacity for innovation and business collaboration, and address the structural and socio-economic challenges that limit the adoption of new technologies in rural areas. In addition, research between producers and companies will allow the establishment of strategic alliances as well as financial support policies and regulations for small- and medium-sized farmers.

Second, to confirm Ecuador's true competitiveness, it is essential to conduct more detailed analyses that complement RCA with other methodologies to ensure an accurate assessment of its position in the global market. It is crucial to promote technological innovation and sustainable agricultural practices to improve the competitiveness of Ecuador's agri-food exports. Collaboration with the FAO and other international organisations can help develop advanced agricultural systems, while promoting products with denominations of origin can add value and improve positioning in global markets.

Third, to achieve greater competitiveness in the agri-food sector in Bolivia, researching the impact of the adoption of new agri-food technologies and practices while accounting for the strategies used by other countries for their competitiveness is crucial. In addition, it is essential to study public policies that can be implemented in the country to improve the sector's production processes and obtain government support.

Fourth, studying the effectiveness of diversification into new agri-food products is crucial to improve the competitiveness of the agri-food sector in Peru. In addition, policies to strengthen market access, actively promote new export markets, both locally and internationally, and make strategic investments in rural infrastructure and advanced agricultural technologies should be explored.

Finally, it is recommended that the results of the RCA Index be used to guide the design of public policies that promote productive diversification, technological innovation, and increased access to international markets for the agri-food sector in the Andean Community. This will improve regional competitiveness and promote sustainable economic development in the member countries. In addition, they will promote academic and diplomatic cooperation to exchange best practices and strategies that promote equitable and sustainable growth of the agri-food sector in the region.

Limitations and future research

The analysis of the export performance of the agri-food sector in the Andean Community member countries reveals several limitations and opens several avenues for future research.

First, RCA analysis requires additional methodological complements to allow a more comprehensive and detailed assessment of the context of each Andean Community member country. As an elementary quantitative study, its methodology could explore the theoretical link with gravity models that verify the impact of the regional integration process on the agri-food sector. In the European and Asian literature, these effects have been studied for several years for variables related to political, economic, and commercial relations. Applying this approach to the Andean context could fill epistemological gaps that have not yet been deeply explored in international relations and economics.

Second, there are discrepancies in the literature regarding the technological factors that determine the competitiveness of the agri-food sector in the Andean Community member countries. While some studies highlight the importance of digitisation and specific technological tools, others have emphasised the relevance of agricultural production and directly applied technology. This variability suggests

the need for more precise and contextualised studies, especially given the progressive application of technologies related to Industry 4.0. In the Andean context, the literature analysing these phenomena is scarce, which undoubtedly limits informed decision-making by both the state and the business sector.

It is noteworthy, therefore, that there is a marked difference in competitiveness factors between developed and developing countries, which points to the need for more detailed comparative studies to help Andean countries improve their government and business practices. Such studies should identify successful practices and strategies that can be adapted to improve the competitiveness of the agri-food sector.

Future research should focus on how different types of technologies (digitalisation, automation, etc.) impact the efficiency and competitiveness of the agri-food sector in various contexts. In addition, it is important to identify the barriers to their implementation and develop solutions to overcome them. Addressing these limitations and exploring the suggested areas of research will allow for a deeper understanding and development of more effective strategies to improve the competitiveness of the sector in the region.

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Authors contributions

R.F.L.T., G.A.B.A., B.B.C.G., C.B.O., M.A.F.L. and J.R.M.C. were responsible for conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, writing original draft, software, supervision, validation, visualization, writing-review and editing. All authors of this paper consent to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author [J.R.M.C] upon reasonable request.

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